

and clear path by encouraging them to self-reflect and set challenging yet realistic goals. Once students reach this stage of independence, they will have developed key skills necessary to succeed academically and beyond.

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ONLINE EDUCATION: WHAT OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES DOES ONLINE EDUCATION PRESENT IN THE FIELDS OF HUMANITIES AND FOREIGN LANGUAGES? HOW CAN TEACHERS ADAPT THEIR TEACHING METHODS AND ASSESSMENT FOR ONLINE FORMATS?

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Annotation: This thesis explores the possibilities and challenges of online education in the realm of humanities and foreign languages. It highlights the benefits of increased accessibility, diversity, and personalized learning experiences that online education offers. It also addresses concerns such as the potential lack of face-to-face interaction, the need for self-motivation and technical skills, and the

variability of online educational resources. The thesis suggests adjustments in teaching methods and assessments to overcome these challenges and create an effective online learning environment.

Keywords: Online education, humanities, foreign languages, accessibility, diversity, personalized learning, face-to-face interaction, self-motivation, technical skills, educational resources, teaching methods, assessments, virtual classrooms, collaborative learning, communication, feedback, engagement, time management, adaptability, digital tools, interactive activities, virtual simulations, multimedia content, online discussions, real-time communication, virtual presentations, collaborative projects, student support, achievement.

In the realm of humanities and foreign languages, online education presents a range of possibilities and challenges. On one hand, the increased accessibility of online education opens up doors for a more diverse and inclusive learning environment, where students from various cultural backgrounds can actively engage with the subject matter and contribute their unique perspectives (Bates, 2019). Furthermore, the flexibility of online learning schedules can be particularly advantageous for adult learners who may have limited availability for traditional classroom-based learning (Dabbagh & Bannan-Ritland, 2005). Additionally, the utilization of adaptive learning technologies allows for personalized learning experiences, tailoring the educational content and pace to individual learners' needs and progress (Garrison & Anderson, 2003).

Moreover, online platforms offer opportunities for interactive and collaborative learning experiences through virtual classrooms, discussion forums, and online group activities, fostering communication and engagement among learners (Moore & Kearsley, 2011). On the other hand, online education also comes with its challenges. One of the primary concerns is the potential lack of face-to-face interaction, which can hinder the development of interpersonal skills and create a sense of isolation for some learners (Palloff & Pratt, 2013). Additionally, online education may require learners to possess self-motivation,

time management, and technical skills to effectively navigate the digital learning environment (Dabbagh & Bannan-Ritland, 2005). Moreover, the credibility and quality of online educational resources and materials may vary, requiring learners to critically evaluate and discern the reliability of the information presented (Bates, 2019).

Online education in the humanities and foreign languages presents challenges, but these can be addressed through adjustments in teaching methods and assessments. Educators can use interactive activities, technology tools, and virtual simulations to facilitate communication and stimulate learning (Garrison & Anderson, 2003). Online quizzes, essays, and presentations can be employed for assessments (Dabbagh & Bannan-Ritland, 2005). Feedback and support from instructors are essential for student engagement and motivation (Palloff & Pratt, 2013). However, challenges remain, such as limited face-to-face interaction impacting language skills and critical thinking (Bates, 2019). Maintaining motivation and time management skills can be difficult in the absence of a physical classroom (Moore & Kearsley, 2011). College professors must recognize and address these challenges by utilizing digital resources, interactive strategies, and timely support to create an effective online learning environment in the humanities and foreign languages.

Online education offers opportunities in humanities and foreign languages. It enhances accessibility, allowing learners worldwide to access educational content (Dabbagh & Bannan-Ritland, 2005). This fosters a diverse and inclusive learning environment. Flexibility in learning schedules accommodates students' responsibilities (Bates, 2019). Adult learners benefit from the freedom to manage their education alongside work or family obligations (Dabbagh & Bannan-Ritland, 2005). Online learning facilitates engaging and collaborative experiences through virtual classrooms, discussion forums, and group activities (Moore & Kearsley, 2011). These opportunities promote communication, cooperation, and active engagement, particularly important in humanities and foreign language education.

Online education in humanities and foreign languages brings opportunities but also challenges. Face-to-face interaction is a crucial aspect of these fields, fostering language skills, critical thinking, and social abilities (Palloff & Pratt, 2013). However, online education may lack the same level of direct interaction, hindering these aspects (Bates, 2019). Motivation and engagement can also be affected, as learners may face distractions and lack the social pressure of a physical classroom (Moore & Kearsley, 2011). Furthermore, the absence of immediate feedback and guidance from teachers can make it difficult for learners to stay on track (Palloff & Pratt, 2013).

Furthermore, online education may require learners to develop effective time management and self-regulation skills (Dabbagh & Bannan-Ritland, 2005). Without the structure and routine of a traditional classroom, learners need to take more responsibility for managing their time and keeping themselves accountable (Bates, 2019). This can be challenging, especially for learners who are not accustomed to self-directed learning.

To optimize online education, college professors must adapt their teaching methods and assessments. They can use digital tools for multimedia content, online discussions, and interactive activities (Garrison & Anderson, 2003). Real-time communication tools enhance virtual classroom interactions (Moore & Kearsley, 2011). Assessment methods should align with the online environment, employing online quizzes, virtual presentations, and collaborative projects (Dabbagh & Bannan-Ritland, 2005). Feedback can be provided through written comments or video, and virtual office hours can address student queries (Palloff & Pratt, 2013). Ongoing reflection and refinement are crucial for effective online teaching (Garrison & Anderson, 2003). Customizing teaching approaches and assessments cultivates an interactive virtual learning environment that promotes student engagement and achievement.

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TA'LIMNING BOSHQARUV YO'NALISHI TALABALARIGA CHET TILINI O'RGATISHDA KOMPETENSIYAGA ASOSLANGAN YONDASHUV

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Abstract: This article discusses the methods and principles of applying a competency-based approach to English language classes in teaching foreign language to management students. Today, competency-based education is very relevant and important.

Key words: foreign language, management, competence, competence, speech, professional, development, standard, education, approach, communicative, intellectual, linguistic, adaptation, teaching.